

SYSTEMATIC-FUNCTIONAL MODEL OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE KNOWLEDGE OF FUTURE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS ABOUT SPORTS TOURISM ON THE BASE OF A COMPETENT APPROACH

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Annotation: This article describes the peculiarities of training future physical education teachers for sports tourism, opinions on the development of various reforms in society.

Key words and phrases: socio-economic, independent education, modern outlook, social necessity, continuous education, physical education teachers, innovative and digital, educational standards, Education and training, scientific-methodical.

INTRODUCTION

Today, modeling the pedagogical process remains one of the urgent tasks. Through this, it will be possible to express the essence of organizing the pedagogical process, the sequence of work to be done. That is why modeling is considered one of the important means of achieving the goal set in pedagogical research. Based on modeling, a model of the researched object is developed. In our research, we relied on the definition of "model" given by I.P. Podlasiy. According to the scientist, the model is a mental image that allows to obtain new information about a certain object, scientifically reflects the subject of research, or a system that is inclined to its material appearance.[1] Today, the concept of "model" is so widely used that it even applies to desired knowledge and ideas about the universe. For example, from a modern point of view, the goal of desired activity can be considered as a model reflecting the result of activity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Models can be classified according to different signs and characteristics. F.I. Peregudov and F.P. Tarasenko grouped models in their research. According to them, models play a very important role in the organization of desired human activity, and it is convenient to distribute all types of activity in the direction of the main volume of information circulating between the subject and the surrounding environment. [2:16] Based on this classification, models can be divided into cognitive and pragmatic groups, depending on the theoretical and practical direction of the goal.

The goal of the research was to develop a pragmatic, systemic-functional model. This type of model is a research that allows future physical education teachers to search for means of managing the process of developing their knowledge of sports tourism, as well as, according to V.A. Slastenin, to achieve the difference between the initial and final state of preparation of students as a model subject. It helps to reflect the functions of managing the processes. [3:512]

In our research, the process of developing the knowledge of future physical education teachers about sports tourism was the object of modeling, and the content and methodical

system of developing the knowledge of future physical education teachers about sports tourism was the subject.

The following functions were considered in the modeling of the required pedagogical system:

- methodological support function. The implementation of this function is related to the regulatory legal documents and the social order that defines the theoretical basis of developing the knowledge of future physical education teachers about sports tourism;
- function of regulatory and legal support. This function requires determining the principles, content, tasks, pedagogical conditions, and diagnostic tools for involving future physical education teachers in activities related to the development of their knowledge of sports tourism;
- methodological support function. It requires clarifying the methodical (content, form, methods and tools) conditions for the future physical education teachers to develop their knowledge of sports tourism;
- practical-applied (empirical) function. This function allows solving a number of tasks: formation of value-oriented principles and stable motives in connection with the development of knowledge, skills, qualifications and competencies of future physical education teachers about sports tourism, analysis of the researched process making and making certain corrections; evaluation and analysis of results, etc.

The following rules were used as the theoretical-methodological basis for modeling the researched process:

- systematic, personal activity-oriented, reflexive approaches;
- theory of pedagogical design, modeling of developmental educational environment;
- theoretical basis of creation of didactic and methodical support;
- formation of axiological direction and the concept of social education;
- theoretical and methodological foundations of the development of voluntary qualities.

The systematic-functional model of future physical education teachers' knowledge development on sports tourism reflected goal-oriented, theoretical-methodological, content-related, organizational and result-oriented components.

The goal-oriented block plays a leading role for other blocks of the system of developing the knowledge of future physical education teachers about sports tourism. Based on the clarification of the content of this block, the educational standard and social order, regulatory and legal bases in the field of research were determined. The goals and objectives of the model were also clarified.

Results

Development of future physical education teachers' knowledge of sports tourism as a social order, the Law "On Education" in the new version, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 28, 2022 "New O for 2022–2026 Decree No. PF-60 "On the Development Strategy of Uzbekistan", higher education was determined by the State Education Standard, as well as by regulatory and legal documents for the development of physical education in higher education.

The analysis of educational standards and legal documents on the training of future physical education teachers shows the need to optimize the educational and pedagogical work aimed at developing future physical education teachers' knowledge of sports tourism in the higher education system. showed.

The goal orientation of the system is determined by the achievement of certain results. Clarification of the goal is carried out by focusing on a number of questions that the developed system should answer. In order to successfully solve the problem of developing the knowledge of future physical education teachers about sports tourism, the final result of this process should be clearly reflected. The purpose of the model was defined in the way of developing the knowledge of sports tourism of future physical education teachers based on the competency approach.

During the development of the model, it was envisaged to solve the following tasks:

- 1) to clarify the methodological approaches to the development of the model for the development of the future physical education teachers' knowledge of sports tourism;
- 2) clarification of the block structure of the model;
- 3) reveal the relationship between the model block and its elements;
- 4) to describe the block structure and elements of the model.

The above-mentioned goals and tasks of developing future physical education teachers' knowledge of sports tourism are related to complex methodological approaches. The concept of methodological approach is interpreted differently by scholars. N.Stefanov defines the methodological approach as a set of principles (system) that defines the general purpose and strategy of activity. interpreted as a strict methodological direction of the research from the point of view of the principle of implementation of the general strategy of the research.[5:352] Pedagogical scientist N. Muslimov emphasizes that the methodological approach should be distinguished from the pedagogic methodology. According to the scientist, the methodological approach is based more on epistemology. This does not yet represent the methodology of pedagogy: "Methodology is not "knowledge or knowledge about knowledge", but "scientific knowledge (theoretical system) about the implementation of activity in a certain field, its methods and tools" should be considered". [6:35]

Supporting the views of educationalists N. Muslimov and N. Yakovlev, it can be said that the approach differs from the method in the following aspects: 1) the approach is more general and less precise; 2) it expresses more formal theories and concepts, general principles and trends; 3) not one, but several methods may correspond to each approach.[7]

The concept of "approach" in its universally recognized essence is expressed as a set of ways and methods used to influence someone, to learn something. The approach to research expresses the main principle and point of view of the researcher.

Effective approaches to developing the knowledge of future physical education teachers about sports tourism can include:

- the systematic-process approach is characterized by setting a problem that reflects the logic of scientific research as the general basis of research, clarifying the main and local goals, clarifying conflicting opinions and points of view, and training future physical education teachers about sports tourism provides development of a model of knowledge development;
- axiological and reflexive approaches, as the theoretical-methodological basis of the strategy, determine the directions of theoretical research, reflect its general view. These approaches make it possible to determine the value system and provide feedback in the system of developing the knowledge of future physical education teachers about sports tourism;
- a personal-activity-oriented approach to determine the mechanism and procedures for organizing the activities of professors and teachers and students, to reveal the

peculiarities of the practical use of the studied phenomenon in order to achieve the set goal. appears as a directed tactic.

Below we explain the essence of these methodological approaches.

Systematic approach is a direction of scientific knowledge and methodology of social practice, which is based on the perception of objects as a system. The systematic approach directs the researcher to reveal the integrity of the object, to identify various types of its connections and to bring them into a unified theoretical view. According to N. Muslimov, the methodological uniqueness of the systematic approach is explained by the fact that it directs research to the following: revealing the integrity of the object and the mechanisms that ensure it; identify different types of complex relationships and bring them to a unified theoretical view; also realizes the vision of a hierarchical system of interconnected models of a complex object, which allows defining the properties of the object's integrity, its structure and dynamics. the uniqueness of the object (system) does not negate the individual characteristics of its components, but rather creates connections and relationships between certain components.

The rules of the systematic-process approach are reflected in the proposed model as follows:

1. The possibility of expressing the research object as a whole, stable and internal self-organizing structure of components, functional communication and a set of relations. The process of developing the knowledge of future physical education teachers about sports tourism as a systematic process is the joint action and interaction of goal-oriented, theoretical-methodological, content-process, organizational, result blocks, their components and their functional interrelationship. It is appropriate to consider it as related.

2. Through the versatility of this approach, management is manifested as a set of interrelated and universal management processes (planning, organization, motivation, control and related processes).[10] In our research, this process is reflected in methodical support (support, friendly attitude, advice and development of future physical education teachers' knowledge of sports tourism).

3. As a result of the training of specialists in higher education, it is aimed at the needs and satisfaction of all consumers of education and achieving its continuous improvement. The best aspect of the system-process approach is reflected in the fact that the "output" results of each process are objectively dependent on the "input" (need) situation. In this way, through the integrity and continuity of all components of this process and model, interdisciplinary communication is achieved in developing the knowledge of future physical education teachers about sports tourism.

Each methodological approach is associated with a certain system of principles that allows the realization of the set goal. The principle means requirements and basic rules for the process of development of pedagogical models, systems, etc. The principles reflect the objective requirements for the formation of the researched direction.

The main principle of the systematic approach considered in the research is the principle of integrity, which requires analyzing the system of developing the knowledge of future physical education teachers about sports tourism both as a whole and as a sum of parts (blocks). This principle is directed to the analysis, to "look at the internal structure" of the system, while preserving the holistic ideas about the system. The model for developing the knowledge of future physical education teachers about sports tourism can be considered as a system consisting of a set of interconnected blocks and elements. This principle allows not only to see

the learner's reaction to a particular behavior, but also to teach him to perceive a separate reality as a part of the whole world.

In the process of research, the systematic-process approach was widely used to develop the knowledge of future physical education teachers about sports tourism. This made it possible to imagine the pedagogical phenomenon under study as a whole in terms of the structures, components, functional relationship and their management occurring in each block of the model. It is possible to create an objective and complete picture of the studied problem based on the synthesis of a systematic and process-related approach. It is characterized by gradualness, controllability and results.

It is also important to use reflexive and axiological approaches in the development of a model for developing the knowledge of future physical education teachers about sports tourism.

The concept of "reflection" is usually considered as the principle of revealing the psychological essence of various phenomena and evidence obtained on the basis of experimental research.

It is reflection that reflects the human ability to create a picture of one's inner world and being. The main specific features of applying a reflexive approach to the process of developing the knowledge of future physical education teachers about sports tourism are reflected in the following:

- making learners directly dependent on the external environment and resistance to it as a subject of some object;
- reflecting the outside world in a volitional activity, motivation, generalized and goal-oriented manner;
- understanding the need to develop voluntary qualities;
- setting a clear goal, that is, putting one's actions into a mental system and imagining its consequences;
- self-control, self-reporting on the situation in the selection situation that occurs in the process of solving professional tasks.

Reflection reflects understanding, comparison, comparison, goal setting, planning, forecasting, self-monitoring, self-evaluation, self-correction.

Applying a reflexive approach to the development of future physical education teachers' knowledge of sports tourism allows to establish active cooperation between students and professors, to realize the individual potential of students in the process of professional formation.

The main principles of the reflexive approach include:

- the principle of self-awareness. Independent personal and professional socialization of students through self-awareness, understanding of the compatibility of one's own needs, opportunities and abilities with the demands of society, preparation for independent, creative and creative activities, internalization of personal and professional value system allows;
- the principle of self-expression. Basing one's moral point of view within the framework of moral standards, taking the initiative in observing ethics in the field of life safety develops the ability to express oneself. By creating a desire for self-development in students, there is an opportunity for self-expression;
- the principle of self-control. This principle is an in-depth analysis, justification and generalization of students' own behavior; the presence of the known and the unknown in connection with a certain situation, the importance of developing voluntary qualities, and the

need to acquire additional competence knowledge in developing voluntary qualities; increases the volitional activity of future physical education teachers, encourages active and independent thinking.

Currently, interest in the axiological approach is related to changes in the socio-cultural environment. The search for new values in connection with changes in society is especially important in the presence of social instability. V. P. Zinchenko emphasizes that the 20th century can be said to be the period of the highest level of devaluation of universal values. [11:340] That is why in the new millennium, the scientific community has to identify, regulate and systematize the values that should be mastered by humanity. is actively moving.

Value orientation also includes the individual's life experiences and dreams. That is why value orientation has its own psychological description and reflects all the components and the whole system of the personality structure.

Scientist B. Khodzhayev, who conducted research in the field of pedagogical axiology, said that a person's understanding of his internal position and readiness for practical activities in connection with specific values determine the essence of a valuable ustanovka. Ustanovka is manifested as a set of cognitive (knowledge, information) and affective (emotion, feeling) components that reflect a person's state of readiness for specific activities.

In connection with the subject of research, the axiological approach is important in terms of forming the value system of future physical education teachers to develop their knowledge of sports tourism.

The research status of the axiological approach allows future physical education teachers to perform various tasks in the systemic-functional model of developing their knowledge of sports tourism: gnostic (identification of socially significant values for the development of voluntary qualities); guiding (selecting the necessary values to satisfy the needs for voluntary activity); information (being aware of the diversity of values related to the development of moral qualities); evaluator (making a correlation between social and personal values); technological (clarification of the ways, methods and means of forming the system of social and personal values); integrative (harmonizing the socially significant values of the pedagogical process and the personal requirements of learners).[12]

The implementation of these functions allows not only the formation of a system of social and personal values, but also the search for ways to resolve them in the personality of each student. Also, the main goal of the axiological approach: in the development of volitional qualities, it creates the necessary conditions for the effective organization of the process of formation of universal, civil, cultural and patriotic values in future physical education teachers.

As the main principles of the axiological approach, the following were defined:

- the principle of integration of social and personal factors that require the formation of a value system in a person. This principle requires future physical education teachers to harmonize social and personal values in developing their knowledge of sports tourism, to ensure integrity between them;
- the principle of social activity. This principle is important and necessary for the development of future physical education teachers' knowledge of sports tourism, and requires the formation of social activity in society, including physical education.

Based on the above-mentioned points, it can be concluded that the reflexive and axiological approach determines the complete description of the process being studied, the effective

planning, organization and diagnosis of future physical education teachers in the development of their knowledge of sports tourism. provides.

Researchers who have conducted research in the direction of the personal-activity-oriented approach say that in the personal-activity-oriented approach, the person and the activity components are closely related to each other, because in the process of this approach, the person as a subject works. In turn, under the influence of various factors and under the influence of the results of the individual's activity, his development as a subject takes place.

Research scientist Sh.Shodmonova stated that it is necessary to analyze the changes that occur in this process based on the identification of the existing factors in the educational process that affect the independent activity of students in a personal-activity-oriented approach. , in which the necessary and sufficient conditions are created for them to express their opinions independently and freely, to express their understanding without any hiccups, to engage in free communication, that is, to show their potential.[12:39]

The following pedagogical conditions were taken into account during the implementation of the personal-activity-oriented approach: the voluntary nature of the student's participation in certain activities; confidence in the student in choosing the means of achieving the set goal, choosing an effective and reasonable strategy in defining educational tasks; prevention of negative consequences arising in the process of pedagogical influence; taking into account the interests of future physical education teachers, their individual enthusiasm, desires and making them develop new interests.

DISCUSSION

Within the framework of the research, an approach focused on personal activity was introduced in practical pedagogical activity based on the following rules: active point of view of future physical education teachers, relying on their independence and initiative; treat the student with respect when communicating with him; the pedagogue should be happy with the success of the students; the pedagogue should help the student to solve important problems; when solving educational tasks step by step, the pedagogue should find options for their implementation that are highly beneficial to each student; In the group and in other groups of students, the pedagogue should form a humanitarian attitude, he should not allow students to be humiliated and lose their morale.

From the point of view of the research subject, the main aspects of the personal-activity-oriented approach were clarified:

1. The development of the knowledge of future physical education teachers about sports tourism depends on the level of content of the motivational-value-oriented component, which determines the orientation of the axiological attitude of the person to the physical will.
2. Organization of an individual approach in the process of developing the knowledge of future physical education teachers about sports tourism requires, in turn, to treat the student's personality as a high value.
3. The organization of the pedagogical process through the use of active forms, methods and tools of education is expressed in harmony with the personal value system.

From an organizational point of view, the need to use a personal-activity-oriented approach requires the following rules to be based on:

- the specificity of developing the knowledge of future physical education teachers about sports tourism requires taking into account the individuality of the person;

- emerges as the basis and practical direction of the content of the development of future physical education teachers' knowledge of sports tourism;
- a personal-activity-oriented approach allows for a complete analysis of the main qualities and unique characteristics of a person.

In this way, a personal-oriented approach forms the basis of the development of methodological support for the process of developing the knowledge of sports tourism for future physical education teachers. This methodological approach requires the following principles:

- the principle of cooperation. This principle organizes the activities of professors and students as equal partners. Therefore, the teacher appears as an experienced teacher who creates conditions for dialogue and exchange of ideas;
- the principle of subjectivity. This principle requires future physical education teachers to have a personal life position on the issue of developing their knowledge of sports tourism. In this process, the professor-teacher helps students understand their "I", think about the consequences of their actions, evaluate themselves as information transmitters, as well as work on the Internet and in the process of communication. must achieve acceptance of the right choice;
- the principle of independence. This principle requires the freedom of future physical education teachers to develop their voluntary qualities based on specific goals and activities.

The personal-activity-oriented approach forms the basis of the content-process block.

The content-process block reflects the following complex pedagogical conditions:

- 1) to determine the social and personal value system in the process of developing the knowledge of future physical education teachers about sports tourism;
- 2) formation of strong willed qualities and a reflexive attitude to future physical education teachers by analyzing situations and completing assignments;
- 3) in the process of preparing educational projects, formation of work experience on the development of voluntary qualities of students in physical education.

Shuningdek, mazkur blok tarkibiga bo'lajak jismoniy tarbiya o'qituvchilarini sport turizmiga doir bilimlarini rivojlantirish ning komponentlari (kognitiv, faoliyatga doir va metodik), pedagogning funksiyalari (informasion, motivasion-fasilitativ, konsultasion) hamda irodaviy sifatlarni rivojlantirishga doir talabalarning vazifalari (adaptasiya, refleksiya, o'z-o'zini namoyon etish)dan iborat metodik ta'minot mazmuni ham taalluqlidir.

Kognitiv komponent o'zida bir nechta o'zaro bir-biri bilan aloqador elementlarni qamrab oladi: 1) o'zlashtirish; 2) qo'llash; 3) umumlashtirish. U sanab o'tilgan jarayonlarni o'zaro aloqadorligini ko'rsatib beradi, ularning mohiyati va mazmunini ochib beradi: irodaviy sifatlarni rivojlantirishga doir bilimlar va qadriyatlarini o'zlashtirish. Mazkur komponent bo'lajak jismoniy tarbiya o'qituvchilari tomonidan irodaviy sifatlarni rivojlantirishga doir bilimlar va qadriyatlar tizimini vaziyatlarni tahlil etish va topshiriqlarni bajarish jarayonida qo'llash bilan ham bog'liq bo'lib, o'quv loyihalarini ishlab chiqish jarayonida mazkur bilimlarni umumlashgan holda foydalanishga erishiladi.

The activity component includes the following three elements: 1) assistance; 2) support; 3) giving advice. It reveals the connection of these processes, their essence, ways of implementation. To support the activity of future physical education teachers as those who need to develop voluntary qualities, to use teaching forms and methods such as seminars, discussions, essays; in the course of activities related to the development of voluntary

qualities, giving advice for independent self-expression is carried out in the process of developing author's educational projects, participating in group discussions, and completing case assignments.

The activity component is a set of mechanisms of mutual action of the professor-teacher and students (cooperation, support, consultation), methodical development closely related to the functions of the pedagogue (informational, motivational-facilitative, consultation). It reveals the organizational forms of supply implementation and the tasks (adaptation, reflection, self-expression) related to the development of future physical education teachers' knowledge of sports tourism.

CONCLUSION.

The methodical component includes forms, methods and means of developing the knowledge of future physical education teachers about sports tourism. It is directly related to the cognitive and activity components and expresses the methodical basis of their implementation. In connection with this aspect, it is possible to come to the following conclusion: the methodical component reflects a set of forms, methods and tools that enable the achievement of the set goal.

The next block of the model reflects the result. This block performs an evaluative function and reflects the practical aspect of the research. Therefore, it reflects the levels, criteria and indicators of future physical education teachers' development of knowledge about sports tourism.

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